

Jejunal Diverticulosis Revealed by Acute Intestinal Obstruction: A Case Report and Literature Review

Anas El Wassi, Kamal Benzidane, Fadoua Zalarh, Abdelhak Ettaoussi, Khadija Kamal, Abdessamad Majd, Mounir Bouali, Abdelillah Elbakouri, Khalid Khaleq, Khalid El Hattabi

Department of General Surgery, Ibn Rochd Hospital, Hassan II University, Faculty of Medicine and Pharmacy, Tarik Ibn Ziad Street, Morocco

Abstract

Introduction: Jejunal diverticulosis is a rare and often asymptomatic condition that presents with vague and nonspecific symptoms, making diagnosis challenging. It is an acquired disorder where the mucosa and submucosa herniate through weakened areas of the intestinal muscle wall. Diagnosis is frequently incidental during imaging or surgery for unrelated conditions.

Case presentation: We report the case of a 52-year-old multiparous woman with a history of right eye surgery, admitted for acute intestinal obstruction. She presented with abdominal pain, cessation of bowel movements, and delayed vomiting. Physical examination showed abdominal distension and tympanism. Imaging revealed small bowel distension with hydro-aerial levels and collapse of the terminal ileum and colonic frame

Management and Outcome : Intraoperative findings showed multiple jejunal diverticula and a strangulated small bowel loop due to parietal adhesions, mimicking an internal hernia. The adhesions were safely released, and the postoperative course was uneventful.

Conclusion: Jejunal diverticulosis, though rare, predominantly affects elderly patients and can be associated with high morbidity and mortality. It should be considered as a differential diagnosis in cases of acute abdomen.

Introduction

Diverticulosis of the small intestine is a rare condition whose management remains controversial [1]. Often asymptomatic and fortuitous discovery, it can be revealed by its infectious or hemorrhagic complications most often requiring emergency surgical management [1].

Similar to colonic diverticulosis, it is considered an acquired diverticulum. This occurs when the mucosa and submucosa protrude through a weakened muscle layer where blood vessels pass through the intestinal wall. 40% of patients remain asymptomatic until complications arise, or the condition is detected accidentally during imaging or surgery for other reasons [1].

This case report describes the incidental discovery of jejunal diverticulosis in a patient presenting with bowel obstruction due to primary adhesion. The article discusses the clinical and paraclinical diagnosis, as well

as the various treatment options available for jejunal diverticulosis.

Patient and Observation

We present the case of a 52-year-old female patient who is multiparous and underwent surgery for an ophthalmological condition in her right eye two years ago. She was admitted to our department with an acute intestinal obstruction. The patient presented with complete cessation of bowel movements, continued passage of gas, diffuse abdominal pain, and delayed vomiting. There were no other associated signs. Physical examination revealed abdominal distension with tympanism. An unprepared abdomen revealed hydroaerial levels in the small intestine. An abdominal-pelvic CT scan revealed distension of the small intestinal loops measuring 44 mm, with hydro-aerial levels present. This was associated with a flattened appearance of the final ileal loop and a few terminal ileal loops, as well as a collapsed colonic frame (figure 1).

More Information

How to cite this article: El Wassi A, Benzidane K, Zalarh F, Ettaoussi A, Kamal K, Majd A, Bouali M, Elbakouri A, Khaleq K, El Hattabi K. Jejunal Diverticulosis Revealed by Acute Intestinal Obstruction: A Case Report and Literature Review. Eur J Med Health Res, 2025;3(4):191-4.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2025.3(4).30

Keywords:

Jejunal Diverticulosis, Diagnosis, Complications, Treatment.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Figure 1: Axial CT Scan Showing the Distension of the Small Intestinal Loops, with Hydro-Aerial Levels

The surgical indication was made in the context of a primary adhesive bowel obstruction, and the patient was urgently transferred to the operating room after a brief stay in the intensive care unit for stabilization.

A midline laparotomy, extending supra- and infra-umbilically, was performed to access the abdominal cavity.

Intraoperative exploration revealed diverticula in the proximal small intestine, extending from 10 to 90 cm from the duodenojejunal angle (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Diverticula in the Proximal Small Intestine

Parietal adhesions caused strangulation of a loop of the small intestine 1.10 m from the duodenojejunal angle (Figure 3), creating an appearance similar to an internal

hernia with distension of the small intestine 6 cm upstream (Figure 4).

Figure 3: The Parietal Adhesions Causing the Internal Hernia

Several uncomplicated sigmoid diverticula were present (Figure 5). A section of the adhesion responsible for the internal hernia was removed without incident.

The postoperative course was uneventful, and the patient was rescheduled for surgery with resection of the small intestine at the site of the diverticula

Figure 4: Distension of the Small Intestine 6cm Upstream

Figure 5: Uncomplicated Sigmoid Diverticula

Discussion

Diverticular disease is a relatively common condition that mainly affects the colon, but to a lesser extent, it can also affect different parts of the small intestine, duodenum, jejunum, and ileum, respectively [2].

Diverticulosis of the small intestine is a rare condition, first described in 1794 by Soemmering and Baille. Its prevalence is estimated at between 0.06% and 4.60% and mainly affects people over the age of 60, with a sex-ratio of 1 [1].

Jejunal diverticulosis may be discovered incidentally, but it is often identified due to complications [3]. Clinical presentations are diverse, such as chronic nonspecific symptoms: intermittent abdominal pain, constipation, diarrhea, dyspepsia, and malnutrition [4]; sometimes, in cases of complications, the disease manifests as acute abdominal pain or gastrointestinal bleeding 10% develop complications such as perforation, obstruction, adhesion, fistula, peritonitis, and lower gastrointestinal bleeding [4]. Acute complications are related to inflammation of the mucosa, which leads to perforation and abscesses [5]. Perforation of jejunal diverticula is a serious complication that occurs in 2–6% of cases [5].

Extended forms have a higher incidence of complications: 38% when diverticula are multiple, compared to 5% when there is only one [1].

Diverticula are pathologically pseudo diverticula, as they are herniated areas of the mucosa and submucosa [3]. The pathophysiology is considered multifactorial, involving intestinal driving forces from luminal contents and peristaltic muscle contractions, as well as sites of weakness in the wall at areas where blood vessels penetrate [5]. This explains their presence exclusively on the mesenteric side [5].

Approximately 50% of patients with jejunal and ileal diverticulosis also have associated colonic diverticulosis, which is better known and easily recognized. This can serve as a warning sign in highly suspicious cases [6].

Diagnosis is often difficult and is mainly confirmed by imaging studies [7].

The jejunum is difficult to examine using endoscopic methods [7]; therefore, radiological methods remain the diagnostic tool of choice. Ultrasound is not suitable for diagnosing jejunal diverticula because it is usually hampered by intestinal gas, which is accentuated by reflexile ileus associated with any intraperitoneal inflammatory process.

CT is currently the best diagnostic imaging method, particularly when using reformatted multiplanar images [7]. It shows pockets in the intestinal wall that may contain air, contrast material, or feces. However, a definitive diagnosis is made through laparoscopy or exploratory laparotomy [2].

No treatment is usually required in cases of incidental discovery in asymptomatic patients. Excision is not generally recommended. The treatment of duodenal and jejunal diverticula differs when patients are symptomatic, depending on the location and clinical presentation of the diverticula, particularly in cases of severe complications such as hemorrhage, perforation, or obstruction. [8]. Non-specific symptoms occurring in an elderly population can lead to a delayed diagnosis, which could explain why this condition is associated with a high mortality rate of 21-40% in cases of perforated diverticulum. According to the findings of Spasojevic and al. published in 2012, conservative treatment is possible in stable patients in the absence of diffuse peritonitis [9]. This is particularly the case with perforations covered by jejunal diverticula. In the absence of a favorable response to medical treatment or in the presence of diffuse peritonitis, surgical exploration, thorough lavage, and segmental resection with primary anastomosis remain the treatment of choice. [10]. Laparoscopy is recommended over laparotomy as the first choice Combining the advantages of a complete exploration of the abdominal cavity with lower post-operative morbidity, particularly in terms of pain and parietal complications, laparoscopy

consists of abdominal cleansing with targeted surgery. Intestinal resection of the diseased segment can be performed through a minimally invasive incision [9].

Conclusion

In conclusion, although diverticular disease of the jejunum is rare, it is important to be aware of this condition because acute complications often require emergency surgery. Some complications, such as acute hemorrhage, can be life-threatening. While conservative management may be effective in the short term, we recommend surgical management of complicated or symptomatic jejunal diverticula, including resection and primary anastomosis, either electively or urgently.

References

- [1] Destan C, Malgras B. Diverticulose du grêle: diagnostic et prise en charge. *Hépatogastro- & Oncologie Digestive*. 2019;26(1):66–74. doi:10.1684/hpg.2018.1718.
- [2] Ibrahim AHM, Amer N, Alattooq HH, AlQatari AA, Abdulmomen AA. Jejunal diverticulosis: a case report. *Int J Surg Case Rep*. 2023 Feb 20;104:107946. doi:10.1016/j.ijscr.2023.107946.
- [3] Dunckley MG, Ahmed K, Said A, Raza M, Dighe S, Al-Temimi A. Variability in the presentation of complicated jejunal diverticulosis. *JRSM Open*. 2023;14(7):1–5. doi:10.1177/20542704231183247.
- [4] Fleres F, Viscosi F, Bertilone E, Mazzeo C, Cucinotta E. Therapeutic strategies for jejunal diverticulitis: our experience and a review of the recent literature. *J Vis Surg*. 2018 Jul 24. doi:10.21037/jovs.2018.07.01.
- [5] Gurala D, Idiculla PS, Patibandla P, Philipose J, Krzyzak M, Mukherjee I. Perforated jejunal diverticulitis. *Case Rep Gastroenterol*. 2020;13(3):521–525. doi:10.1159/000503896.
- [6] Andour H, Loubaris S, Zahi H, Imrani K, Nassar I, Moatassim Billah N. Jejunal diverticulosis: a rare diagnosis with serious complications. *Radiol Case Rep*. 2024 Nov 6;20(1):556–559. doi:10.1016/j.radcr.2024.10.016.
- [7] Zafouri EB, Ben Ismail I, Sghaier M, Rebi S, Zoghliami A. Jejunal diverticulitis: a new case report and a review of the literature. *Int J Surg Case Rep*. 2022 Jul 9;97:107395. doi:10.1016/j.ijscr.2022.107395.
- [8] Kuzmova M, Salame M, Colonval P. Diverticule jéjunal perforé et abcédé: revue de la littérature. *Louvain Med*. 2021 Oct;140:400–403.
- [9] Spasojevic M, Naesgaard JM, Ignjatovic D. Perforated midgut diverticulitis: revisited. *World J Gastroenterol*. 2012 Sep 14;18(34):4714–4720. doi:10.3748/wjg.v18.i34.4714.
- [10] Hubbard TJ, Balasubramanian R, Smith JJ. Jejunal diverticulum enterolith causing perforation and upper abdominal peritonitis. *BMJ Case Rep*. 2015;2015:bcr2015210095. doi:10.1136/bcr-2015-210095.

